

Three-Dimensional Modeling and Performance Analysis of a Fuel Cell-Based Direct Methanol Fuel Cell Short-Stack

Emre Kaplan and Rachel Patel

Emre Kaplan, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sabanci University, Istanbul, Turkey; Rachel Patel, Department of Energy Systems and Nuclear Sciences, University of Calgary, Calgary, AB, Canada

Abstract

One of the primary challenges in fuel cell stack models, is the lack of numerical methods and computational resources available to handle a full-scale stack geometry to at least the same grid resolution and detailed physics as could be obtained in an equivalently detailed single cell model. To help resolve this challenge, a 3D modelling approach is proposed, and applied to a 3-cell Flowing Electrolyte-Direct Methanol Fuel Cell (FE-DMFC) short-stack. In this approach, the flow fields, backing layers and membranes are solved numerically in a 3D manner, whereas the electrochemical performance is solved analytically. This approach allowed for the detailed physics to be incorporated into the model without the requirement of a high mesh density within the MEA, thus softening the computational load. The methanol concentration distributions at the anode catalyst layer of each cell for different methanol concentrations and sulfuric acid flow rates were found. In addition, the changes of crossover current density and cathodic activation polarization with current density were assessed. The model was used to shed light onto the mechanisms that lead to non-uniform flow behaviour within the stack's cells; help identify methods to maintain a uniform flow and concentration distribution within the stack; and to provide methods to minimize methanol crossover to the cathode.

Indexed keywords: Short-stack, FE-DMFC, flow distribution, stack model.

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1. Introduction

The direct methanol fuel cell (DMFC) is one of the low temperature fuel cell types that can be used in grid-independent portable applications. Methanol, being in the liquid form, is easy to achieve and store, and has a high energy density. However, being a toxic material, special care has to be given in the selection and design of the methanol containers. DMFC technology also has some challenges towards its widespread commercialization, such as low performance due to the slow reactions at the electrodes, the methanol crossover problem, and the high cost of catalyst. In a conventional DMFC, Pt-Ru/C, Pt-C, Nafion® 115, carbon paper or cloth, and graphite are used as the materials of the anode catalyst, cathode catalyst, membrane, backing layer, and flow field respectively. There has been ongoing research on the selection of materials for catalysts, catalyst supports and membranes, and other designs to improve the performance of DMFCs [e.g. 1–6]. In a report by Zelenay [7], it was given that 0.56 V at 0.15 A·cm⁻² was achieved with the following design and operating conditions: Pt:Ru atomic ratio of

1:4 (JMFC's advanced anode catalyst), anode catalyst loading of $1.0 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, Pt/C cathode catalyst loading of $1.5 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, Nafion® 115 membrane, cell temperature of $88 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, methanol concentration of 0.6 M , air in the cathode. In a recent paper by Wan [8], a high maximum power density ($320 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) was achieved employing a very thin membrane (Nafion XL, which is $27.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). In his study, PtRu/C (PtRu loading of $2.3\pm 0.05 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) and Pt/C (Pt loading of $2.3\pm 0.05 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) from Tanaka Kikinokuni were used as the anode and cathode catalysts, respectively.

A DMFC stack, which is formed by bringing many DMFC single cells together, can be designed in different ways. These differences arise from using different flow patterns and flow field types in the stack. A U-shaped (inlet and outlet are at the same side of the stack) or a Z-shaped flow pattern (inlet and outlet are at the opposite sides of the stack) can be selected [9]. A suitable configuration of a flow field should be selected, which yields an optimal pressure drop, uniform reactant distributions across the corresponding electrodes, and the effective removal of the products. Depending on the active area, a variation of a serpentine, parallel or pin design are generally used as the flow field type. In a recent study by Ozden et al [10], different bio-inspired flow field designs were used in either one side or both sides of the fuel cell for performance comparison purposes. In addition to the performance, the durability is a key indicator for the success of a stack. Zelenay [7] reported that advanced JMFC anode catalyst coated membranes (with an active area of 50 cm^2) were used in a 10-cell stack and tested at SFC Energy. They reached the maximum stack voltage after 70 hours of operation and a decay rate of $19 \text{ }\mu\text{V}/\text{h}$ (per cell) was seen in around 2,800 hours of operation.

The performance decrease due to methanol crossover can be eliminated by using a different DMFC design, namely the Flowing Electrolyte-Direct Methanol Fuel Cell (FE-DMFC). In this fuel cell type, a porous channel, in which a proton conducting substance (e.g. sulfuric acid) flows, is located between two half-MEAs. The flow of this substance removes the unwanted methanol crossover from anode to the cathode. Hence, the cathodic activation loss decreases. However, the additional flowing electrolyte channel and membrane increase the total Ohmic polarization of the cell. There has been numerous modeling and experimental studies (e.g. [3, 11-21]) that mainly investigate the effect of different design and operating parameters for this fuel cell type. Recently, Colpan et al. [3] showed that FE-DMFC can decrease the methanol crossover significantly; and Faradaic efficiencies up to 98% can be achieved.

Mathematical models of fuel cells have been developed on the cell, stack, and system-level with different levels of complexity in the literature. On the cell-level, the aim is either to model a repeat element, which is generally taken as the portion of the DMFC around of a single channel found in the middle of the flow field, or the complete single cell which contains all of the geometrical details of the flow field. On the stack-level, different approaches can be used. For large-stacks, a flow distribution model can be used to determine the pressure and flow distribution for each cell; whereas for short-stacks, more detailed (including the geometrical details of the flow pattern and configuration) and higher-dimensional models (e.g., from 1D to 3D) can be developed. On the system-level, fuel cell and other components are generally considered to be zero-dimensional (0D). Analytical solutions are generally applied if 0D or 1D modeling techniques are applied, whereas numerical solutions are generally applied for 2D or 3D (single phase or two-phase) modeling approaches. Although there are many modeling studies

on hydrogen-fueled proton exchange membrane fuel stacks in the literature (e.g. [22-29]), there are a limited number of studies on the modeling of DMFC stacks in the literature. For example, Argyropoulos et al. [30] developed a two-phase DMFC stack model to describe its hydraulic behavior. Using this model, the pressure drop of each cell and the flow distribution through the internal manifolds were found. Wang et al. [31] developed a DMFC stack model using an adaptive network-based fuzzy inference systems method. The main inputs of their model were temperature, methanol concentration and current; whereas the cell voltage was the output. They showed the importance of selecting the values of methanol concentration and temperature to obtain high values of fuel utilization. Scott et al. [32] developed a DMFC stack model to predict several important performance parameters such as the stack voltage, overall system pressure, and fluid distribution from the flow manifolds. On the other hand, there is only one study for modeling of a FE-DMFC stack. Kablou [33] designed and manufactured a five-cell flowing electrolyte-DMFC stack having a parallel serpentine flow field design and U-type manifold configuration. He used an analytical, iterative approach, namely “Hardy Cross” method, for this purpose. He showed that the flowing electrolyte effectively reduces the methanol crossover, allowing the performance of the stack to be enhanced.

The literature survey showed that there is no mathematical model of a FE-DMFC that accounts for the detailed stack geometry and transport phenomena. For this purpose, a 3D modelling approach is applied to a 3-cell FE-DMFC stack. The pressure drop across the anode and cathode flow fields, and the distributions of velocity and methanol concentrations are found for different methanol concentration (1 M, 2M and 4 M) and flowing electrolyte flow rates (1 mL/min, and 10 mL/min).

2. Computational model

2.1. Computational domain

The three dimensional computational domain consists of a 3-cell FE-DMFC short-stack with a U-type manifold for the anode flow field (AFF) and the flowing electrolyte channel (FEC), and a Z-type manifold for the cathode flow field (CFF), as shown in Fig. 1a. Each cell has an active area of 25 cm², whereas each anode flow field consists of a parallel, serpentine design (5 channels; Fig. 1b), and each cathode flow field consists of a straight parallel design (25 channels; Fig. 1b). The MEA, shown in the sub-figure of Fig. 1a, consists of an anode and cathode backing layer (ABL and CBL, respectively), catalyst layer (ACL and CCL, respectively; each considered as an interface), anode and cathode membranes (AM and CM, respectively; each considered to be completely liquid-equilibrated), and a FEC.

Fig. 1: (a) Computational domain of the entire 3-cell FE-DMFC short stack used in this study. The sub-figure shows the considered MEA. (b) and (c) represent the anode and cathode flow fields, respectively.

2.2. Modeling assumptions

To model the previously described computational domain, the following assumptions were made:

- The fuel cell stack operates under steady state, isothermal and single phase conditions.

- The effects of gravity are assumed negligible.
- All fluids are considered to be laminar, ideal and exist in equilibrium with one another.
- Each media is homogeneous and isotropic.
- The catalyst layers are sufficiently thin to be considered as an interface.
- The membranes are fully liquid-equilibrated and impermeable to the gaseous phase.
- All crossed over methanol is fully consumed at the cathode catalyst layer-cathode membrane interface.
- The mass transfer within the porous layers are diffusion-dominant.

2.3. Modeling equations

In a previous publication of the authors [12], the governing equations for a steady state, isothermal and single-phase FE-DMFC model were given. In this section, a summary of these equations is given.

Three conservation equations are used in this model: the conservation of mass (Eq. (1)), momentum (Eq. (2)), and species (Eq. (3)); applied to methanol and oxygen).

$$\rho(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) = S_{gen} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\rho \mathbf{u}}{\varepsilon^2} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot \left[-P \mathbf{I} + \frac{\mu}{\varepsilon} \langle (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) + (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})^T \rangle - \frac{2\mu}{3\varepsilon} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{I} \right] - \left[\frac{\mu \mathbf{u}}{K} + \frac{S_{gen} \mathbf{u}}{\varepsilon^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \left[-D_i^k (\nabla C_i^k) \right] + \mathbf{u} (\nabla C_i^k) = S_{gen,i}^k \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (1), ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{u} is the superficial velocity within the porous layers, and S_{gen} is the mass source term associated with the chemical reactions within the catalyst layers. Within Eq. (2), ε is the porosity, P is the pressure, \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, μ is the dynamic viscosity, and K is the absolute permeability. Within Eq. (3), D is the molecular diffusivity (corrected for the porous structure via the Bruggeman equation), C is the molar concentration, and $S_{gen,i}^k$ is the molar source term of an arbitrary species k in phase i . It should be noted, that for simplicity, convection is only considered within the channels.

To calculate each of the cell's voltages, V_{cell} , the reversible cell voltage, V_{rev} , is subtracted from each of the respective cell's loss mechanisms (i.e.: the anode [a] and cathode [c] activation [η_{act}] polarizations, as well as the cell's Ohmic polarization [η_{Ω}]), as given by Eq. (4).

$$V_{cell} = V_{rev} - \eta_{act,a} - \eta_{act,c} - \eta_{\Omega} \quad (4)$$

The anode activation polarization is estimated from the anodic Meyers-Newman (non-Tafel) equation (Eq. (5)), whereas the cathode activation polarization is obtained from the Tafel equation (Eq. (6)) [10].

$$\eta_a = \frac{\bar{R}T}{\alpha_a F} \ln \left[\frac{i \cdot C_{l,ACL}^M}{i_{a,ref} \cdot C_{l,ACL}^M - i \cdot K_a} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_c = \frac{\bar{R}T}{\alpha_c F} \ln \left[\left(\frac{i + i_{xover}}{i_{c,ref}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{C_{g,ref}^{O_2}}{C_{g,CCL}^{O_2}} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

Here, \bar{R} is the universal gas constant, T is the cell temperature, α is the charge transfer coefficient, F is Faraday's constant, K_a is the methanol oxidation reaction constant, i_{xover} is the crossover current density (obtained from Eq. (7)). The terms within the square brackets of this equation, represents the methanol's molar permeation rate to the cathode, accounting for the diffusive and electro-osmotic transport mechanisms) and i_{ref} is the reference exchange current density. The methanol and oxygen concentrations are measured at the CL surface, with the subscript *ref* referring to the reference concentration.

$$i_{xover} = 6F \left[-D_e^M (\nabla C_l^M) + \left(\frac{n_d^{H_2O}}{C_l^{H_2O}} \frac{i}{F} \right) C_l^M \right] \quad (7)$$

The Ohmic polarization is calculated using Ohm's law, where the cell resistance calculated from Eq. (8); which accounts for the ionic resistance of the anode and cathode catalyst layers, the membranes, and the FEC.

$$R = \frac{1}{\kappa_e} \left[t_{AM} + t_{CM} + \frac{t_{ACL}}{\epsilon_{e,ACL}^{1.5}} + \frac{t_{CCL}}{\epsilon_{e,CCL}^{1.5}} \right] + \frac{t_{FEC}}{\kappa_{e,FEC} \epsilon_{e,FEC}^{1.5}} \quad (8)$$

The following boundary conditions were implemented to solve the governing equations (Eqs. (1) to (3)):

- No slip and normal flux conditions on all the channel walls
- A methanol concentration and normal oxygen flux of zero at the cathode membrane – CCL interface
- A gauge pressure of 0 Pa at the anode and cathode manifold outlets
- A known volume flow rate and reactant concentration at the anode, cathode and flowing electrolyte manifold inlets.

2.4. Mesh generation and solution procedure

The computational model is developed in COMSOL Multiphysics® 5.0, which is a commercially available finite element solver. The governing equations are implemented using the software's built-in modules ("Free and Porous Media Flow" for Eqs. (1) and (2), and "Transport of Diluted Species" for Eq. (3)), whereas the remaining constitutive equations are manually entered as user defined functions. An unstructured tetrahedral mesh of ~15 million elements, is used in this study. Three different segregated groups (one for each of the species [methanol and oxygen], and

one for the pressure and velocities) are configured to solve the set of equations. Each group is solved using the multifrontal massively parallel sparse (MUMPS) direct solver. Once the simulations are complete, the average quantities in each layer (e.g.: concentration, pressure and velocity) are outputted using probes. These quantities are used to analyze the simulation results as well to calculate of the fuel cell's electrochemical performance using Eqs. (4) - (8).

3. Results and Discussion

The model developed for the FE-DMFC stack is simulated to find the pressure drop across the AFF and CFF, velocity and species distributions, and to assess the effect of methanol concentration and flowing electrolyte flow rate at the inlet. The design and operating parameters for the baseline conditions are shown in Table 1; whereas the electrochemical parameters are shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Design and Operating Parameters for the Baseline Conditions.

Design Parameters	
Thickness of ABL and CBL	175 μm
Thicknesses of ACL and CCL	20 μm
Thicknesses of AM and CM	127 μm
Thickness of FEC	175 μm
Porosity of ABL and CBL	0.78
Porosity of AM and CM	0.20
Porosity of FEC	0.78
Permeability of ABL and CBL	10^{-12} m^2
Permeability of AM and CM	10^{-18} m^2
Permeability of FEC	10^{-12} m^2
Operating Parameters	
Flow rate of methanol at the anode manifold inlet	10 mL/min
Flow rate of sulfuric acid at the flowing electrolyte channel manifold inlet	1 mL/min
Flow rate of oxygen at the cathode manifold inlet	1200 mL/min
Concentration of methanol at the anode manifold inlet	2000 mol/m^3
Concentration of sulfuric acid at the flowing electrolyte channel manifold inlet	2000 mol/m^3
Concentration of oxygen at the cathode manifold inlet	47 mol/m^3
Cell temperature	70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

Table 2. Electrochemical Properties used Within this Study.

Electrochemical Properties	Value
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Methanol oxidation coefficient	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mol/m}^3$
Reference oxygen concentration	47.32 mol/m^3
Anode reference exchange current density	0.70 A/m^2
Cathode reference exchange current density	0.02 A/m^2
Anode charge transfer coefficient	0.239
Cathode charge transfer coefficient	0.875
Membrane resistance	$7.1033 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Ohm} \cdot \text{m}^2$
ACL and CCL resistance	$6.8078 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Ohm} \cdot \text{m}^2$
FEC resistance	$2.5791 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Ohm} \cdot \text{m}^2$
Electrolyte water content	$22 \text{ H}_2\text{O}/\text{HSO}_3^-$
ACL and CCL electrolyte volume fraction	0.30
Ionomer conductivity	17.8790 S/m
Sulfuric acid conductivity	98.5 S/m

In a fuel cell stack, it is desirable to minimize the pressure drops between the inlet and exit of the flow fields. Low pressure drops reduce the power consumption in some of the auxiliary components such as the pump and the blower. In addition, the pressure drops between each cell of the stack should be close to each other to provide uniform flow distribution in the cells. For the baseline conditions, the pressure drops across the AFF and CFF are shown in Figs. 2a and 2b, respectively, each for low (250 A/m^2) and high (3000 A/m^2) current density conditions. As can be seen from these figures, the AFF pressure drop increases by 0.10 Pa (from 40.31 Pa) from Cell-1 to Cell-3; whereas the CFF pressure drop decreases by 1.00 Pa (from 164.13 Pa) from Cell-1 to Cell-3 when the current density is taken as 250 A/m^2 . For the AFF (which has a U-shape manifold), Cell-3 is closest to the manifold inlet and outlet, allowing for more fluid flow to travel through this cell. On the otherhand, Cell-1 is furthest from the manifold inlet and outlet, causing the pressure to decrease along both the inlet and outlet manifolds, making the difference in pressure lower. As such, less fluid travels through this cell, and by extension, any cells further away from the inlet and outlet manifolds. For the CFF (which has a Z-shape manifold), Cell-1 is closest to the outlet manifold. Furthermore, because there is only a small pressure drop along the inlet manifold, this allows for the greatest pressure drop and thus flow to travel through Cell-1. For Cell-3, on the other hand, the pressure drop along the outlet manifold decreases the pressure difference across Cell-3, as seen in Fig. 2b. When the current density is taken high, it can be seen that the pressure drops increase slightly for each cell, which occurs because of the momentum exchange caused by the electrochemical reactions taking place. On the other hand, the pressure drop in the FEC is found to be significantly higher than that in the AFF and CFF (14363 Pa) because the flow within the FEC is through a thin and long porous channel, whereas the anode and cathode channels are non-porous. Furthermore, the trend in the pressure distribution was found to be the same as that in the AFF because they shared the same manifold design (U-shaped). However, in this case, there was only a 1.3 mPa pressure difference between Cell-3 and Cell-1, because of the presence of the porous substrates. This small pressure difference

allowed for a uniform flow distribution between each cell. Any large pressure variations between cells might only be observed in large-scale FE-DMFC stacks.

Fig. 2: Pressure drop in the a) anode flow field and b) cathode flow field for the baseline conditions.

For the cell found in the middle of the stack (Cell-2), it was found that there was little difference between the flow distribution between one anode parallel serpentine channel to the next (Fig. 3a); where the maximum pressure difference between the middle channel and the outer-most channel was 55.6 mPa at an inlet flow rate to the stack's anode of 10 mL/min. This small pressure difference seems to indicate that the effects of under-rib convection is small for the examined flow rate and that the flow within the ABL is diffusion-driven. However, within the cathode's parallel channel configuration (Fig. 3b), it was found that the channels within the middle of the CFF received the least amount of flow. For example, with an inlet flow rate to the stack's cathode

of 1200 mL/min, the middle channels obtained a maximum velocity of 4 mm/s, whereas the outer-most channels obtained a maximum velocity of nearly 1100 mm/s. This difference in velocity distribution between channels is primarily attributed to the fact that at the cell's inlet, the bulk flow's momentum is directed along those first channels. As the flow travels along the top and bottom collector channels, the pressure difference becomes comparable, leading to very little flow being transported across the middle channels. Towards the cell's outlet, the pressure difference now becomes high due to its proximity to the cell's outlet, this forces the bulk flow to be transported through the last few channels. This indicates that the flow predominately travels along the first and last few channels. Similar results were also obtained for the other cells. It was also found that the velocity distribution within the AFF and CFF were independent of current density. This was due to the fact that the model assumed that the thermophysical properties (density and viscosity) were constant throughout the simulations, and the flow was assumed to be single phase. Considering how the methanol concentration is relatively low (predominately composed of liquid water) and that the concentration of oxygen did not change significantly within the considered current density range, the constant thermophysical property assumption is considered reasonable. However, as the current density is increased, the generation of the secondary phase (gaseous carbon dioxide within the anode, and liquid water within the cathode) increases. The presence of this secondary phase is expected to change the velocity and pressure distributions, due to the relative motion between phases, as well as any drag imposed by the two phases at their two-phase interface. However, the overall trends in the predicted stack performance, within the range of operating conditions considered in this work, are expected to be the same.

Fig. 3: The velocity distribution for a) the anode [mm/s] and b) the cathode [m/s] flow fields of Cell-2 for the baseline conditions.

In a conventional DMFC, the inlet methanol concentration typically ranges between 500-1000 mol/m³ to reduce the negative effects of methanol crossover, and thus increase the performance of the cell. However, higher methanol concentrations at the inlet are generally desirable in order to reduce the fuel storage tank volume, and to increase the energy density of the fuel. In recent publications (e.g., [34]) on FE-DMFC modeling at cell-level, it has been shown that this fuel cell type can handle high methanol concentrations. In this study, the effect of methanol

concentration at the inlet is assessed for a 3-cell FE-DMFC stack. Methanol concentration distributions at the anode catalyst layer are presented for each cell, for the case of an inlet methanol concentration of 1000 mol/m^3 and 4000 mol/m^3 , as shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. In each of these cases, the sulfuric acid flow rate was 1 mL/min , and the current density was 1000 A/m^2 . These figures show that the methanol concentration varied between 191 mol/m^3 and 745 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 190 mol/m^3 and 746 mol/m^3 (Cell-2), and 30 mol/m^3 and 668 mol/m^3 (Cell-3). The average methanol concentrations at the ACL for the given conditions are 578 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 578 mol/m^3 (Cell-2) and 437 mol/m^3 (Cell-3). These results show that the Cell-3 has the least uniform methanol concentration because the least amount of flow traveled through this cell (lowest stoichiometric flow rate to this cell), as discussed at the beginning of this section. The uniformity of Cells-1 and 2 were found to be very close to each other. Increasing the inlet methanol concentration from 1000 mol/m^3 to 4000 mol/m^3 , it can be seen that the trend for the methanol concentration distribution between each cell does not change significantly. For this methanol concentration, the average methanol concentrations at the ACL are found as 2311 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 2311 mol/m^3 (Cell-2) and 2170 mol/m^3 (Cell-3).

Fig. 4: Methanol concentration distributions [mol/m^3] at a methanol inlet concentration of 1000 mol/m^3 , sulfuric acid flow rate of 1 mL/min , and current density of 1000 A/m^2 and at the anode catalyst layer surface for a) Cell-1, b) Cell-2, and c) Cell-3.

Fig. 5: Methanol concentration distributions [mol/m^3] at a methanol inlet concentration of 4000 mol/m^3 , sulfuric acid flow rate of 1 mL/min , and current density of 1000 A/m^2 and at the anode catalyst layer

surface for a) Cell-1, b) Cell-2, and c) Cell-3.

The flow rate of sulfuric acid flowing through the flowing electrolyte channel affects the methanol reaching the CCL. In single-cell FE-DMFC studies (e.g., [3,15-16,21,34]) found in the literature, higher flow rates of sulfuric acid have been shown to yield better cell performance as the crossover current density and the cathodic activation polarization decrease with an increase in this flow rate. However, higher sulfuric acid flow rates also increase the power demand of sulfuric acid pump and thus the electrical efficiency of the FE-DMFC system decreases. For a 3-cell FE-DMFC stack, the effect of sulfuric acid flow rate on the behavior of the stack is assessed. Figs. 6 and 7 show the methanol concentration distributions at the ACL for a methanol inlet concentration of 2000 mol/m^3 and a current density of 1000 A/m^2 for a sulfuric acid flow rate of 1 mL/min and 10 mL/min , respectively. It can be seen from these figures that the methanol concentration changes between 382 mol/m^3 and 1490 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 379 mol/m^3 and 1491 mol/m^3 (Cell-2), and 220 mol/m^3 and 1412 mol/m^3 (Cell-3) when the sulfuric acid flow rate is 1 mL/min ; whereas this concentration changes between 232 mol/m^3 and 1306 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 227 mol/m^3 and 1306 mol/m^3 (Cell-2), and 93.6 mol/m^3 and 1244 mol/m^3 (Cell-3) when the sulfuric acid flow rate is 10 mL/min . The results also show that increasing the sulfuric acid flow rate, the average methanol concentration at the ACL decreased from 1155 mol/m^3 to 912 mol/m^3 (Cell-1), 1156 mol/m^3 to 912 mol/m^3 (Cell-2) and 1014 mol/m^3 to 801 mol/m^3 (Cell-3) when the sulfuric acid flow rate increases from 1 mL/min to 10 mL/min . These findings show that when the FEC flow rate is increased, the concentration of methanol at the AM-FEC interface decreases. This occurs because the higher FEC flow rate removes more methanol from the FEC, creating a higher concentration difference across the AM, leading to a higher diffusive flux of methanol across the AM. This increased flux of methanol is also shown to lead to low concentration pockets under the channels' ribs for the high FEC flow rate case, potentially leading to decreased cell durability. Furthermore, even though the rate of methanol crossover through the AM increases with increasing FEC flow rate, the convective flux of the incoming sulfuric acid causes a lower methanol crossover flux through the CM; for instance, at open circuit voltage, the maximum crossover current density was 2839 A/m^2 (1 mL/min) and 786 A/m^2 (10 mL/min).

Fig. 6: Methanol concentration distributions at a methanol inlet concentration of 2000 mol/m^3 , sulfuric acid flow rate of 1 mL/min , and current density of 1000 A/m^2 and at the anode catalyst layer surface for a) Cell-1, b) Cell-2, and c) Cell-3.

Fig. 7: Methanol concentration distributions at a methanol inlet concentration of 2000 mol/m^3 , sulfuric acid flow rate of 10 mL/min , and current density of 1000 A/m^2 and at the anode catalyst layer surface for a) Cell-1, b) Cell-2, and c) Cell-3.

For the parameters studied in this paper, the changes in crossover current density and cathodic activation polarization of the cell found in the middle of the FE-DMFC stack with respect to current density are shown in Figs. 8 and 9, respectively. It can be seen from these figures that for a fixed sulfuric acid flow rate (1 mL/min), increasing the methanol concentration increases the crossover current density and the cathodic activation polarization. On the other hand, for a fixed methanol concentration (2000 mol/m^3), increasing the sulfuric acid flow rate decreases the crossover current density and the cathodic activation polarization. Of these combinations, the lowest values for these parameters were found for the 2000 mol/m^3 methanol and 10 mL/min sulfuric acid flow rate case (lower methanol concentrations at this high flow rate were not examined). The cause of this behaviour follows the same reasoning as provided in the previous paragraph. However, the reduction in the cathode activation polarization at high FEC flow rates is caused by the decreased rate of methanol permeation rate to the cathode, whereby the decreased crossover current density decreases the surplus rate of oxygen consumption within the CCL. As such, these results show that the sulfuric acid flow rate should be selected to be sufficiently high for a given methanol concentration to improve the performance of the stack. It was also found that the results for the change of crossover current density and cathodic activation polarization with respect to current density did not change for the other cells.

Fig. 8: The change of crossover current density with current density for different methanol concentration and sulfuric acid flow rate values for Cell-2.

Fig. 9: The change in cathodic activation polarization with current density for different methanol concentration and sulfuric acid flow rates for Cell-2.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a 3D modelling approach is proposed, and applied to a 3-cell Flowing Electrolyte-Direct Methanol Fuel Cell (DMFC) short-stack. The mass and species transport were solved in a 3D manner; whereas the electrochemical performance of the fuel cell was solved analytically. The conservation of mass, momentum and chemical species, and the electrochemical relations were all coupled and solved numerically using a commercially available software, namely Comsol

Multiphysics. The main conclusions derived from this study are as follows:

- The cells furthest from the outlet manifold in a U-shaped configuration have the least amount of flow. This lead the anode (which used a U-shaped manifold) methanol concentration distribution to have a low uniformity in these cells.
- The porous FEC had a significantly higher pressure drop than the AFF and CFF. However, the porous FEC material allowed for a uniform pressure, and thus flow distribution between cells.
- Under the examined operating conditions, the pressure difference between adjacent parallel serpentine channels are very small causing little under-rib convection. This allows for the species transport to be efficiently modeled as diffusion-dominated within the BLs.
- Lower inlet methanol concentrations led to better performance for a fixed sulfuric acid flow rate.
- Lower crossover current densities, and thus lower cathode activation polarizations, can be achieved with high sulfuric acid flow rates.

References

1. Brandão L., Rodrigues J., Madeira L. M., Mendes A., Methanol crossover reduction by Nafion modification with palladium composite nanoparticles: Application to direct methanol fuel cells, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 35(20), 11561-11567, (2010).
2. Casalegno A., Santoro C., Rinaldi F., Marchesi R., Low methanol crossover and high efficiency direct methanol fuel cell: the influence of diffusion layers, *Journal of Power Sources*, 196(5), 2669-2675, (2011).
3. Colpan C. O., Ouellette D., Glösen A., Müller M., Stolten D., Reduction of methanol crossover in a flowing electrolyte-direct methanol fuel cell, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, (2017).
4. Liu G., Zhou H., Ding X., Li X., Zou D., Li X., Wang X., Lee, J. K., Effect of fabrication and operating parameters on electrochemical property of anode and cathode for direct methanol fuel cells, *Energy Conversion and Management*, 122, 366-371, (2016).
5. Mondal S., Soam S., Kundu P. P., Reduction of methanol crossover and improved electrical efficiency in direct methanol fuel cell by the formation of a thin layer on Nafion 117 membrane: Effect of dip-coating of a blend of sulphonated PVdF-co-HFP and PBI, *Journal of Membrane Science*, 474, 140-147, (2015).
6. Seo S. H., Lee C. S., A study on the overall efficiency of direct methanol fuel cell by methanol crossover current, *Applied Energy*, 87(8), 2597-2604, (2010).
7. Zelenay P., *Advanced Materials and Concepts for Portable Power Fuel Cells*, US DOE Hydrogen Program Annual Merit Review and Peer Evaluation, (2012).
8. Wan, N. High performance direct methanol fuel cell with thin electrolyte membrane. *Journal of Power Sources*, 354, 167-171. (2017).
9. Barbir F., *PEM fuel cells: theory and practice*, Academic Press. (2012).
10. Ozden A., Ercelik M., Ouellette D., Colpan C. O., Ganjehsarabi H., and Hamdullahpur F., Designing, modeling and performance investigation of bio-inspired flow field based DMFCs, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, (2016), doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.01.007.
11. Ouellette, D., Matida, E., Cruickshank, C.A., "The Effect of Water Introduction Rate and Liquid Saturation Jumps on the Performance of the Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell", *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Vol. 42, (2017), 13913-13926.

12. Ouellette, D., Gencalp, U., Colpan, C.O., “Effect of Cathode Flow Field Configuration on the Performance of the Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Vol. 42, (2017), 2680-2690.
13. Atacan, O.F., Ouellette, D., Colpan, C.O., “Two-Dimensional Multiphase Non-Isothermal Modeling of a Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Vol. 42, (2017), 2669-2679.
14. Ouellette, D., Colpan, C.O., Matida, E., Cruickshank, C.A., “Parametric Studies on the Membrane Arrangement and Porous Properties of the Flowing Electrolyte Channel in a Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. Vol. 40, (2015), 7732-7742.
15. Ouellette, D., Colpan, C.O., Matida, E., Cruickshank, C.A., “A Single Domain Approach to Modeling the Multiphase Flow within a Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. Vol. 40, (2015), 7817-7828.
16. Ouellette, D., Colpan, C.O., Matida, E., Cruickshank, C.A., Hamdullahpur, F., “A Comprehensive 1D Model of a Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell with Experimental Validation”, *International Journal of Energy Research*. Vol. 39, Issue 1, (2015), 33-45.
17. Kablou, Y., Cruickshank, C.A., Matida, E., “Experimental Analysis of a Small-Scale Flowing Electrolyte–Direct Methanol Fuel Cell Stack”, *Journal of Fuel Cell Science and Technology*, Vol. 12, (2015), 41007-1 - 41007-7.
18. Duivesteyn, E., Cruickshank, C. A., Matida, E., “Nonisothermal Hydrodynamic Modeling of the Flowing Electrolyte Channel in a Flowing Electrolyte–Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *Journal of Fuel Cell Science and Technology*. Vol. 11, (2014), 021011-1 - 021011-6.
19. Ouellette, D., Cruickshank, C.A., Matida, E., “Experimental Investigation on the Performance of a Formic Acid Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, *Journal of Fuel Cell Science and Technology*. Vol. 11, Issue 2, (2013), 26–33.
20. Colpan, C. O., Fung, A., Hamdullahpur, F., “2D Modeling of a Flowing Electrolyte Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, 209, (2012), 301-311.
21. Colpan, C. O., Cruickshank, C. A., Matida, E., Hamdullahpur, F., “1D Modeling of a Flowing Electrolyte-Direct Methanol Fuel Cell”, 196, (2011), 3572-3582.
22. Chang P., Kim G. S., Promislow K., Wetton B., Reduced dimensional computational models of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell stacks, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 223(2), 797-821, (2007).
23. Fang L., Di L., Ru Y. A dynamic model of PEM fuel cell stack system for real time simulation, In Power and Energy Engineering Conference, APPEEC 2009. Asia-Pacific (pp. 1-5). IEEE, (2009).
24. Kvesić M., Reimer U., Froning D., Lüke L., Lehnert W., Stolten D., 3D modeling of a 200 cm² HT-PEFC short stack. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 37(3), 2430-2439, (2012).
25. Kong X., Khambadkone A. M., Modeling of a PEM fuel-cell stack for dynamic and steady-state operation using ANN-based submodels, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, 56(12), 4903-4914, (2009).
26. Liu Z., Mao Z., Wang C., Zhuge W., Zhang Y., Numerical simulation of a mini PEMFC stack. *Journal of Power Sources*, 160(2), 1111-1121, (2006).
27. Philipps S. P., Ziegler C., Computationally efficient modeling of the dynamic behavior of a portable PEM fuel cell stack, *Journal of Power Sources*, 180(1), 309-321, (2008).
28. Musio F., Tacchi F., Omati L., Stampino P. G., Dotelli G., Limonta S., Davide B., Grassini P., PEMFC system simulation in MATLAB-Simulink® environment, *International Journal of*

Hydrogen Energy, 36(13), 8045-8052, (2011).

29. Shimpalee S., Ohashi M., Van Zee J. W., Ziegler C., Stoeckmann C., Sadeler C., Hebling C., Experimental and numerical studies of portable PEMFC stack, *Electrochimica Acta*, 54(10), 2899-2911, (2009).

30. Argyropoulos P., Scott K., Taama W. M., Modeling flow distribution for internally manifolded direct methanol fuel cell stacks, *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, 23(11), 985-995, (2000).

31. Wang R., Qi L., Xie X., Ding Q., Li C., Ma C. M., Modeling of a 5-cell direct methanol fuel cell using adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference systems, *Journal of Power Sources*, 185(2), 1201-1208, (2008).

32. Scott K., Argyropoulos P., Taama W. M., Modelling transport phenomena and performance of direct methanol fuel cell stacks, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 78(6), 881-888, (2000).

33. Kablou Y., Hydrodynamic Modelling and Experimental Analysis of FE-DMFC Stacks, MSc Thesis, Carleton University, Ottawa, Canada, 2012.

34. Ouellette, D., "Multiphase Modeling of a Flowing Electrolyte – Direct Methanol Fuel Cell", PhD Thesis, Carleton University, (2015).